

ADDRESSING

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Annontation: *The article deals with the expression of connotation in the English and Uzbek literary texts proceeding from the pragmatic approach to the analysis. In the paper the utterances selected from the English and Uzbek literary texts manifest the expression of various shades of connotation on the phonetic, phonological, lexical, morphological and syntactical levels of the language.*

The analysis of the English and Uzbek literary texts shows that in spite of the fact that English and Uzbek languages belong to different typological systems and different genealogical families there are a lot of common similarities in expressing connotation. On the basis of the pragmatic approach to the analysis of expressing connotation the authors use the method of Allan Keith (the professor of linguistics at Monash University (Australia)) and Speech Act Theory by John Austin. Key words and expressions: literary competence, evaluate, reproduce, literary taste, skill of conveying, interlocutor, cultural and national mind, coordination of sounds, emphatic intonation, phonological level, syntactic level, lexical level, stylistic peculiarities, pragmatic approach, similarity. The language is a social phenomenon, which is used to express social actions of speakers, their communicative competence so that they should exchange ideas, thoughts, feelings and impressions. In literature language is used to express emotional purposes so that the readers should enjoy the author's production. Cognitive analysis of literary texts manifests emotive effect of literary interpretation, feelings which meet the demands of the readers. Pragmatic analysis of literary texts shows that production and interpretation of the text are the process where the author and the reader take part. In this process the reader plays an active role as though taking part in the event created by the author. Depending on his literary competence the reader understands, evaluates and reproduces the author's production. That is why the author thinks about the reader so that there should be fixed a mutual and sensible context which will help the reader to understand the literary work. The author uses

his skill of writing the literary text so that the reader should be able to use his knowledge, experience and literary taste in order to understand and contemplate. Different meanings may be expressed from the same utterance depended on the author's intention, his purpose so that he should have the skill of conveying the connotative meaning in all levels of the language [2]. The professor of linguistics at Monash University (Australia) Allan Keith [2] says that connotations have pragmatic effects that motivate semantic extension. Connotation invites associations of words to other words and their evaluative aspects, or affective meaning. So evaluation is expressed by the author and concretized either in positive, negative or neutral aspect [2]. Allan Keith says that denotation may seem to be part of an utterance, but connotation indwells any expression of language [2]. Pragmatic approach to the study of grammatical units can be briefly described as the study of the way, the language is used in particular contexts to achieve particular goals [7]. Speech Act Theory was first introduced by John Austin who says that the notion of a speech act presupposes that an utterance or purposes can influence the reader and situation in different ways [7]. For example, in the utterance It's cold here we can concretize the following purposes according to the position or the context this utterance is used: 1) The speaker just states the fact; 2) The speaker wants the interlocutor to do something about it (close the window or switch on the heating system); 3) The speaker shows that he is displeased with the interlocutor's not having heated the room; 4) The speaker is seeking for an excuse so that he should not do something his interlocutor wants him to; 5) The speaker wants to blame the interlocutor for the latter's not having heated the room. The analysis of the utterance It's cold here shows that in order to concretize the meaning expressed by the utterance it is reasonable to use the method of pragmatic analysis in the process of defining the connotative meaning conveyed by the speaker. The author, performing a speech act, takes into consideration the knowledge of his reader so that there should be constructed a mutual understanding which comprises two levels: the first level includes interaction inside the fictional world, the second includes interaction where the author and the reader take part. That is why various speech acts, thoughts are performed by the same utterance in fiction, one and the same utterance gives different linguistic interpretations [2]. Connotation was dealt with in the works by Teliya V.N. [20, p. 5], Comlev N.G. [11], Kolshanskiy G.V. [10, p. 93-95], Arnold I.V. [5], and there were given different interpretations to the language phenomenon connotation. As the language reflects the cultural and national mind of the people the language of whom is spoken of, connotation expresses different emotional expressive,

conceptive, metaphoric and symbolic meanings added to the sound, word, expression, grammatical form or the statement used in the text, the attitude of the speaker to his action or the reality as well. Connotation is the language phenomenon expressed on some level of the language which arises people to a pleasant or unpleasant judgment, touch emotions of the reader or the listener. The analysis of the examples taken from literary texts of the English and Uzbek languages show that connotation is expressed on the phonetic, phonological, lexical and grammatical levels of the language. In the examples given below the connotation expressed on the phonetic level of the language is demonstrated: 1. “Whenever the moon and stars are set, Whenever the wind is high, All night long in the dark and wet, A man goes riding by” (R.S.Stevenson) The repetition of the sound [w] produces expressiveness, it makes the fact more emotional and touchable. 2. “Deep into that darkness peering, long I stood there, wondering, fearing, Doubting, dreaming dreams no mortals ever dared to dreams before.” (E.A.Poe) In this example the repetition of the sound [d] merely suggests that a certain amount of information is contained in the repetition of the sound as the case with the repetition of lexical units do. L. Bloomfield, a well-known American linguist says that “...in human speech different sounds have different meanings. To study the coordination of certain sounds with certain meanings is to study language” [8, p. 27] 3. What a wonderful day! As we see in this sentence the rising intonation adds additional colour to the expressed thought, makes it emotional, gives the reader or the listener the feeling of pleasure. A.A. Abduazizov says that emphasis is capable of expressing not only ideas of contrast and intensity, but also various shades of meaning. Usually emphatic intonation is typical in jokes, anecdotes, comic remarks, irony, teasing etc. [1, p.197]. Emotional means of intonation express the speaker’s attitude towards the fact in question, his feeling, emotions and moods.

